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STEGANOGRAPHY BASED ASYMMETRIC KEY CRYPTOSYSTEM USING TRELIS CODED GENETIC ALGORITHM RANDOM KEY GENERATOR

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on generating a random bit sequence using Trellis coded Genetic Algorithm (TCGA) with boolean function as source of input. Randomness of the generated bit sequence is tested using the methods proposed by National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) to be used as random key for cryptographic applications. Generated random key is transmitted using Blue Pixel Least Significant bit (BPLSB) steganographic technique. The extracted random key is then used for image encryption and decryption for asymmetric key cryptosystem.

KEYWORDS

Genetic Algorithm, Image Encryption, Random Key, Steganography, Trellis Code

For More Details : <http://wireilla.com/papers/ijesa/9119ijesa01.pdf>

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Enhanced Embedded Linux Board Support Package Field Upgrade – A Cost Effective Approach

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ABSTRACT

Latest technology, new features and kernel bug fixes shows a need to explore a cost-effective and quick upgradation of Embedded Linux BSP of Embedded Controllers to replace the existing U-Boot, Linux kernel, Dtb file, and JFFS2 File system. This field upgrade technique is designed to perform an in-the-field flash upgrade while the Linux is running. On successful build, the current version and platform specific information will be updated to the script file and further with this technique the file system automates the upgrade procedure after validating for the version information from the OS-release and if the version is different it will self-extract and gets installed into the respective partitions. This Embedded Linux BSP field upgrade invention is more secured and will essentially enable the developers and researchers working in this field to utilize this method which can prove to be cost-effective on the field and beneficial to the stake holder.

KEYWORDS

Embedded Linux, Upgrade, Kernel, U-boot, JFFS2 File system.

For More Details : <http://wireilla.com/papers/ijesa/9119ijesa02.pdf>

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A VLSI Architecture Realisation of an Wireless Endoscopy System

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ABSTRACT

The main objective is to design a VLSI architecture to realize an wireless endoscopy system. This system is used in medicinal field by recording images of the digestive system. It is developed to transfer the image data using the RF transmission so as to avoid the pain and irritation to the digestive tract which can be caused by the cables when using conventional endoscopes. The proposed system consists of a RF transceiver and a CMOS color image sensor. Capturing of images is done by image color sensor. RF transceiver is used to send the images wirelessly. CMOS color image sensor is interfaced with FPGA. Real time images captured by the color image sensor are compressed and they are sent wirelessly by the RF transceiver. Image compression is used since it is the best way to save the power in transmission and reception and to decrease the bandwidth in communication. So, after capturing the image using the CMOS color image sensor, the image is compressed. Compression is done by JPEG standard. After high-quality lossy compression, the image is transmitted by the wireless RF transceiver. Wireless transceiver is chosen in such a way that it is operated in low power.

KEYWORDS

Image compression, JPEG-LS, CMOS, RF & FPGA

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